

A Study on the Impact of Modern Digital ERA

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Abstract

While there are many useful ways of describing and discussing the Digital Era, explanations of its existence are lacking. The Digital Era is characterized by technology which increases the speed and breadth of knowledge turnover within the economy and society. Evolutionary theory, as an explanation of the system we live in, states that sustainability relies on knowledge turnover. In parts of the system which are relatively stable, knowledge turnover is low, and new variation, when produced, is rarely retained. In other, less stable parts of the system, faster knowledge turnover is advantageous as new knowledge is produced more frequently allowing for adaptation to the changing surrounding environment. Mixing and matching rates of knowledge turnover makes for a dynamic but ever-lasting world. The Digital Era can be seen as the development of an evolutionary system in which knowledge turnover is not only very high, but also increasingly out of the control of humans, making it a time in which our lives become more difficult to manage. For example, in the second generation Internet, 'the semantic web', functionality, which understands meaning, replaces the search function of unknowingly matching words, which often have multiple meanings. In time, within this version of the Internet, software agents will exchange knowledge without human intervention. Equally, our understanding of the knowledge embedded within the human genome about how we relate to the world, generated in association with technology and freely available on the Internet, raises questions about our assumptions of control. Do we know enough about our future to change our genome? Can we control such changes and their diffusion? The social and economic implications of the Digital Era are huge and will increase as technological functionality becomes more knowledge-based, our everyday lives and understanding of ourselves become more linked to it, and it takes on a 'life' of its own. Understanding the Digital Era in terms of evolution will help ensure we build sustainable socio-economic relationships both with technology and with the advanced knowledge that technology helps us create.

Introduction

A socio economic comprehensive presentation of the main characteristics and findings of a "transformation theory" with respect to post-communist in Central and Eastern Europe (CEE) might seem easier than the task really is. On the one hand, the notion "transformation" does not represent the only conceptual term in the field as the competitive notions "transition" and "reform" demonstrate. This is a hint at the contested subject as well as the alternative basic theoretical assumptions and competing theoretical currents.

On the other hand, the general possibility of a transformation theory and, assumed that there is such a possibility, its type and range keep a field of intensive debate. Against this background, it is impossible to offer here either an overview of "the analytical paradigm of transformation theory" or a description of the state of the art in the post-communist transformation studies.

This article tries rather to deliver a sketch of a particular theoretical position on the subject of transformation. This position is a sociological one, and more concrete: a position of a historical-sociological theory of societal transformations. Even under this limitation, the following theoretical considerations must confine themselves to the outline of a conceptual framework. It starts with the definition of societal transformations.

(1.) and goes on with the discussion of focal points and theoretical-methodological tools of the approach (2.) Then some concrete contributions of the approach for the analysis of CEE with respect to the socio-economic processes and problems will be presented (3.) The last part (4.) deals briefly with the question, whether we need a distinguished theory of post-communist capitalism.

Societal Transformations

What does it mean? The notion „transformation“ owes its rise the political and social ruptures in CEE after 1989 and normally refers – often without any further adjective – to the post-communist social changes in this region. From a historical-sociological perspective, I plead for an extension of the frame of reference. In my view, societal transformations represent a specific type of social change that should be grasped as an alternative way of formational change compared with the “classical” forms like the formation of modern democratic and capitalist societies in the north western hemisphere over last three hundred years. The first historical and to some extent paradigmatic case of societal transformations was the so-called “Meiji-Restoration” in Japan (1867-1912). Later, many other attempts under different conditions and with plural directions of system change followed. Three distinct waves and four types of societal transformations can be differentiated: “post-feudalist transformations” (1867 until the first decades of the 20th century), “state-socialist transformations” and “post-colonial transformations” (after the WWII up to the 1970s) as well as post-socialist transformations.

Review of Literature

A good way to start and examine the role of state in socio economic transformation and development. Ralph and Milliband Nicos were some of economist defines the socio economic transformation and that function to serve capitalist interests. Argued in state functions in 1973 through economic and political regime.

Evans (1995): discussed the role of state in cultivating and nurturing entrepreneurial forces directly in productive activates Evan by doing this agued over the socio transformation in states. Computer in digital started from many reforms have been digitalised.

Government must play important role to ensure that everyones enjoy inetervention in the economic transformation of justified on the grounds targeted at protecting the reforms.

Developmental State

The concept of development state is largely attributed to Johnson (1982) who used the ministry of international trade to discuss how the socioeconomic transformation has been developed. States engaging developing process from developed countries.

States engaged in shaping progressively the development process are sometimes led to by state business relations.

Objectives of Socio Economic Transformation

The digital era has transformed the way of many of us live and work by creating society and economy.

- The structure of the era means people developed in countries.
- Over time the digital era will have same effect on members of society and economics.
- Digital era based on evolutionary theory specifically the branch called memetics which helps in social evolution.
- The digital social and economic transformation.

Statement of Problem

This section reviews two emerging realities in which economy and society combine to produce knowledge in a way that can be accounted for and explored within the social evolution frame work. The cases of challenge the ability of humans to control in the world and involve cases in different systems.

Issues and Policies of Socio Economic Transformation

Issues based on Agriculture	1970	1980	1990	1999
APEC	58.6	357.7	901.6	1904.9
EU	76.5	456.9	981.3	1376.3
NAFTA	22.5	102.2	26.3	581.2
EAEC	9.2	13.4	28.6	81.9
SAARC	0.1	0.6	0.9	621.6

Socio economic reforms based on agricultural credit friendly banking policies pursued by reserve bank and subsequently NABARD government of India there has been significant increase in flow of bank credit agriculture in digital basis.

Flow of credit from agriculture and industry and socio economic reforms has been developed.

Year	Amount of Outstanding to Agriculture	Amount of Outstanding to Industry	Amount of Outstanding to TTM
1980	3722 (15.7)	5777 (57.7)	3167 (31.6)
1990	16626 (15.9)	11555 (48.8)	8397 (35.5)
1995	24948 (11.80)	50486 (45.6)	3684 (35.3)
1999	40889 (9.9)	18797 (49.1)	89780 (42.5)

The agriculture in total bank credits both direct and indirect which stood in 10.7 has been declined to 9.9 percent in 2000 noticed that bank credit for agriculture has been reduced too much socio economic transformation.

Need for the Study

The research came from the attention of primary cities have been paid attention to urban areas to develop socio economic transformation and have carried out in recent times their emerging dynamics and resulting development patterns.

The rapid urbanization of cities in has developed early 1980s followed pattern increasing development in urban areas over the decade has transformed for growth in socioeconomic transformation in digital basis in urban areas.

Limitations of Socio Economic Transformation

The worlds economic system are gaining currently through a number of transformation process of more or less dramatic nature. These particular processes which have been taking place in the post. Socialist part of the globe and perhaps the most vivid among all those that change the worlds economy and societies. Certainly the fundamental character of changes entailed by post social transition provides a motivation for returning to study of many issues of which have already sometime ago dropped the study of many issues based on socioeconomic transformation on and digital basis economic thought includes new evidence. The transition economics offer test they are tested based on concepts and theories and how the digital era work in socioeconomic transformation observing the unique courses and events in socio economic transformation.

Economic Transformation:-Real Sector

Real sector policy measures mainly focused on manufacturing sector in early stages of reform process. Deregulation of industry by way of eliminating licensing requirement overhauling of public enterprises, enhanced in private sector, abolition of MRTP act automatic approval route for foreign investment, elimination of quantitative import restrictions. And reduction in tariff rates created a conducive environment to gear up the industry to face growing domestic as well as external competition to which it is exposed by the reform process.

The boom in information technology (IT) information technology and enabled services (ITES) sector essentially led an era of “service growth “as India emerged as global hub for service in the world. IT to an extent has generated the employment opportunities for both skilled and unskilled labours.

Large consumer goods companies directly source agricultural produce from farmers. While these development have worked towards improving (TOT) was also strengthening by lowering of protection for manufacturing sector and market determined price.

Economic Transformation:- Financial Sector

Reforms in financial sector complimented the real sector development. transformation financial sector not only assisted in sharp pick up services sector growth, it helped the manufacturing sector to progress from cost to international segment of economy. It was a clear recognition of role of market forces in price discovery process. Prior to these reforms, pricing of financial resources hardly reflected the underlying situation capital scarce economy.

Money Market

Reforms in money market were essentially aimed at providing avenues for the players to deploy or access to short term funds and platform to the monetary authority to modulate the liquidity system. Liberalisation measures in money market preceded the over all reform process of deregulation of interest rates and introduction of new instruments. Were initiated in 1980s A series of steps over year freeing of interest rates on call and other money market instruments.

Capital Market

Like other market segments there have been far reaching changes in both primary and secondary market segments of capital market. Tribal areas under going socio economic transformation in Himachal: study Shimla: some of the tribal areas in Himachal are undergoing significant socioeconomic development changes in terms of literacy, educational patterns, societal structure and other aspects according to study, socio economic development in tribal areas of HP since inception of tribal sub plan 1974 conducted under the aegis of Indian council of social science research (ICSSR) by a geographer of Himachal Pradesh University (HPU).

Transformation in economics refers to a long term change in dominant economic activity in terms prevailing relative engagement or employment of able individuals

Conclusion

Evolutionary theory is knowledge based evolution means changes in the proportion of different knowledge over time where knowledge is defined as that creates relation of socio economic transformation in whole world.

The theory states that the world we live in made up of subsystem all of which evolved from previously evolved subsystems. These entire sub systems are knowledge based and survive because each contains mechanism by new knowledge is produced without knowing future.